

Supplementary Tables and Figures

Table S1: The number of clinical isolates in each lineage carrying each known SLID-R marker, regardless of phenotypic DST. The lineage of 12 isolates could not be determined, including one isolate with *eis*:C-14T, and one isolate with *rrs*:A1401G. One other isolate belonged to *M. Africanum* species, West African 1 lineage.

	Indo-Oceanic	East-Asian	East-African Indian	Euro-American
<i>rrs</i> :A1401G	7	181	6	66
<i>rrs</i> :G1484T	1	1	2	0
<i>eis</i> :C-12T	0	54	0	53
<i>eis</i> :C-14T	0	25	0	3
<i>eis</i> :G-10A	3	47	3	2
Total	68	700	53	350

Table S2: Isolates carrying multiple known SLID-R markers. “Isolate” reports each isolates ID number. “AMK,” “KAN,” and “CAP” report the isolate’s phenotypic drug susceptibility testing (DST) results for amikacin, kanamycin, and capreomycin, respectively. “R” indicates resistance, “S” indicates the isolate is susceptible, and “ND” indicates there was no phenotypic DST available for the isolate for the drug.

Isolate	AMK	KAN	CAP	Mutations	Lineage
2393-05	R	ND	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-14T	East-Asian
TB1236	R	ND	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	Euro-American
2-0062	R	R	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	Euro-American
2-0006	R	R	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	Euro-American
1314-05	R	ND	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	East-Asian
6335-05	R	ND	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	East-Asian
3176-10	R	R	ND	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	East-Asian
10529-05	R	ND	ND	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	East-Asian
9975-05	R	ND	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	East-Asian
TB1237	S	ND	S	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	Euro-American
TB0908	R	ND	R	<i>rrs</i> :G1484T, <i>eis</i> :G-10A	Indo-Oceanic
2-0063	R	R	R	<i>eis</i> :C-12T, <i>eis</i> :C-14T	Euro-American
TB0179	S	ND	S	<i>eis</i> :G-10A, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	East-Asian

Table S3: Contingency table comparing isolates with full SLID cross-resistance and known SLID-R markers. SLID-R markers are enriched among fully SLID cross-resistant isolates, with an odds ratio of 97.45 (95% CI 43.26-2258.38, p-value < 2.2e-16, Fisher’s Exact Test).

	Carries Known SLID-R Marker	No Known SLID-R Marker	Totals
Fully SLID cross-resistant	186	7	193
Not Fully cross-resistant	60	223	283
Totals	249	230	476

Figure S1: Association of *tlyA* genotype with capreomycin resistance. This reports the number of capreomycin resistant (dark blue) and susceptible (light blue) clinical *M. tuberculosis* isolates with each non wild type genotype in the *tlyA* gene. Isolates with variants in the *rrs* gene were positioned in the right side of the graph. Isolates with mutations in the *eis* promoter were not included, due to no isolate having mutations in *eis* and *tlyA* simultaneously.

Table S4: Mutation-based analysis in genes previously implicated to cause second-line injectable drug resistance. For each suggested gene, the number of unique variants exclusive to any unexplained resistant isolate and absent in any susceptible isolate were counted. The antibiotic it is associated with and the sensitivity of each mutation are also included.

^a Corresponds to the main gene

^b Corresponds to the gene promoter

Gene	Variant	Drug	# of Unexplained Resistant Isolates	Sensitivity
<i>bfrA_prom</i>	G-63GC	AMK	1	0.286
<i>bfrB_prom</i>	A-12G	AMK	1	0.286
<i>Rv2005c</i>	R286W	AMK	1	0.286
<i>Rv3848</i>	CA832C	AMK	1	0.286
<i>tuf</i>	D209E	AMK	1	0.286
<i>whiB6</i>	C34S	AMK	1	0.286
<i>whiB7_prom</i>	AC-55A	AMK	1	0.286
<i>atpA</i>	GC1580G, R142	CAP	1 for each variant	0.290 for each variant
<i>bfrA, bfrA_prom</i>	H28P ^a , G-63GC ^b	CAP	1 for each variant	0.290 for each variant
<i>bfrB_prom</i>	A-12G	CAP	1	0.290
<i>hspX</i>	H137R	CAP	1	0.290
<i>moxRI</i>	A11	CAP	1	0.290
<i>prcA</i>	CA186C	CAP	1	0.290
<i>Rv0148</i>	L171	CAP	1	0.290
<i>Rv1258c</i>	P310	CAP	1	0.290

<i>Rv2005c</i>	R286W	CAP	1	0.290
<i>Rv3848</i>	CA832C, T228, R219S	CAP	1 for each variant	0.290 for each variant
<i>whiB6</i>	C34S	CAP	1	0.290
<i>whiB7</i> , <i>whiB7_prom</i>	E69A ^a , A-57C ^b , CA-57C ^b , AC- 55A ^b	CAP	1 for each variant	0.290 for each variant
<i>35kd_ag</i>	R230W	KAN	2	0.671
<i>atpA</i>	GC1580G, GC197G	KAN	1 for each variant	0.335 for each variant
<i>bfrA_prom</i>	G-63GC	KAN	1	0.335
<i>lpdC</i>	N157	KAN	1	0.335
<i>Rv1258c</i>	A367T	KAN	1	0.335
<i>Rv3848</i>	CA832C	KAN	1	0.335
<i>tig</i>	G59	KAN	2	0.671
<i>whiB7</i> , <i>whiB7_prom</i>	TGCGCGGACG TCC250-261T ^a , E69A ^a , C-56T ^b , CA-57C ^b , A- 57C ^b , C-55T ^b , AC-55A ^b , GT- 161G ^b , T-116C ^b	KAN	1 for each variant	0.335 for each variant

Table S5: Genome position of regions with known resistance markers. This table lists boundaries of genomic regions inspected for known SLID-R markers in *M. tuberculosis* clinical isolates. These genome positions are in respect to reference genome, H37Rv.

Gene	Genome Position	Orientation
<i>rrs</i>	1471846 to 1473382	+
<i>eis promoter</i>	2715332 to 2715532	-

Supplementary Methods

DNA Extraction and Sequencing

The DNA of all 333 isolates collected for long-read PacBio sequencing, including those of Stockholm and Antwerp, and from NCBI's SRA database were extracted as described in previous studies¹. In brief, isolates were cultured on Lowenstein-Jensen (LJ) media, followed by killing with ethanol and heat. The collected isolates were sequenced with the Pacific Biosciences (PacBio) Single Molecule Real Time (SMRT) long read sequencing platform. The SMRT sequencing protocol was described previously². In brief, PacBio's DNA Template Prep kit without follow-up PCR amplification was used with subsequent DNA shearing. The sheared DNA was end repaired and hairpin adapters were ligated with the use of T4 DNA ligase resulting in a final sample library with insert sizes of 20 kilobases. SMRTbell templates were subjected to standard SMRT sequencing using an engineered phi29 DNA polymerase on the PacBio RS system, as stipulated in PacBio's protocol.

Genome Assembly, Alignment and Variant Calling

To process the original GCDD PacBio long-read data, first raw reads were aligned to the *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv reference strain (Genbank accession number NC_000962.3) utilizing SMRT Analysis's Basic Local Alignment with Successive Refinement (BLASR) with default parameters (v1.3) (<https://github.com/PacificBiosciences/blasr>). Then PBHoover, our custom software³, corrected aligned reads and called variants based on a maximum likelihood criterion. Finally Variant Effect Predictor⁴ (VEP) (v87) determined the consequence of each variant and annotated the VCF formatted files. The 269 clinical isolates, including the 10 isolates from Stockholm and Antwerp, were processed with a new pipeline. Raw reads were *de novo* assembled via the Hierarchical Genome Assembly Process version 2 (HGAP2,

RS_HGAP_Assembly.2 protocol; <https://github.com/PacificBiosciences/Bioinformatics-Training/wiki/HGAP-2.0>) using default parameters, or via Canu⁵. Circularization was performed with minimus2 (<https://github.com/sanger-pathogens/circlator/wiki/Minimus2-circularization-pipeline>) using default parameters with a previously written protocol or circlator⁶ v1.4.0 with the ‘all’ command and --genes_fa flag set to the H37Rv *dnaA* sequence. Error correction was performed as previously described². Three rounds of consensus polishing were performed using BLASR with default parameters, and Quiver with a maximum coverage of 1000, using the RS_Resequencing protocol from SMRTAnalysis v2.3 (<https://www.pacb.com/wp-content/uploads/SMRT-Analysis-Software-Installation-v2-3-0.pdf>). Failed isolates were excluded from this paper.

To call variants, dnadiff v1.3 (<https://github.com/marbl/MUMmer3/blob/master/docs/dnadiff.README>) aligned each assembled genome to *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv (NC_000962.3) and call SNPs and small indels with default parameters. A custom Perl script converted the out.snps into a VCF v4.0 file and the Variant Effect Predictor⁴ (v87) determined the consequence of each variant.

To process the 851 downloaded Illumina short-read data sequences, first trimmomatic⁷ (v0.36) trimmed adapters from raw reads and removed low quality ends. Next bowtie2⁸ (v2.2.4) aligned the reads to the *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv reference sequence (Genbank accession NC_000962.3). SAMtools (v1.3.1) (<http://samtools.sourceforge.net/>) then sorted, filtered out reads with a mapping quality of less than 20, and created an mpileup file for each isolate. VarScan2⁹ (v2.3) called and filtered variants with a minimum quality of 20, a minimum depth of 10, the strand filter set to false, and otherwise default parameters. Variant consequence was

determined by VEP⁴. Isolates with less than ten reads for VarScan2 to call variants at the sites of resistance mutations listed in Table 1 were excluded from the study.

References

1. van Helden PD, Victor TC, Warren RM, van Helden EG. VTC. 2001. Isolation of DNA from *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Methods Mol Med* 54:19–30.
2. Elghraoui, A., Modlin, S.J. & Valafar, F. SMRT genome assembly corrects reference errors, resolving the genetic basis of virulence in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *BMC Genomics* 18, 302 (2017).
3. Ramirez-Busby, S. M., Elghraoui, A., Kim, Y. B. & Valafar, F. PBHoover and CigarRoller: a method for confident haploid variant calling on legacy Pacific Biosciences data and its application to heterogeneous population analysis. *Bioinforma.* - *Under Rev.* 1–27 (2018).
doi:10.1101/360370
4. McLaren, W. et al. The Ensembl Variant Effect Predictor. *bioRxiv* 042374 (2016).
doi:10.1101/042374
5. Koren, S. *et al.* Canu: scalable and accurate long-read assembly via adaptive k-mer weighting and repeat separation. *Genome Res.* **27**, 722–736 (2017).
6. Hunt, M. et al. Circlator : automated circularization of genome assemblies using long sequencing reads. *Genome Biol.* 1–10 (2015). doi:10.1186/s13059-015-0849-0
7. Bolger, A. M., Lohse, M. & Usadel, B. Trimmomatic: A flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence data. *Bioinformatics* 30, 2114–2120 (2014).

8. Langmead, B. & Salzberg, S. L. Fast gapped-read alignment with Bowtie 2. *Nat. Methods* **9**, 357–359 (2012).
9. Koboldt, D. C. *et al.* VarScan 2: somatic mutation and copy number alteration discovery in cancer by exome sequencing. *Genome Res.* **22**, 568–576 (2012).